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Review Article

COMMON ADVERSE EFFECT OF DRUG USED TO TREAT TUBERCULOSIS

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ABSTRACT:

One of the oldest known diseases to afflict humans, tuberculosis (TB) is a leading cause of death globally and is brought on by bacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex.

According to the WHO, tuberculosis is the second leading cause of death worldwide after HIV/AIDS, and it remains a serious threat to human health. The poor socioeconomic segment of the population and the marginalized segments of the community are particularly susceptible to tuberculosis. The national objective of India's National Strategic Plan (2017–2025) is to eradicate tuberculosis by 2025. It calls for a greater knowledge and comprehension of tuberculosis. The introduction to disease, epidemiology, type of tuberculosis, pathogenesis, adverse drug reaction of drug and how to overcome them have all been covered in this review article.

The diagnostic methodology for PTB and EPTB, as well as a wealth of specific information about diagnostic modalities, have been explained. The treatment plans for drug-resistant, adverse drug reaction, and nutritional support, along with the latest medications suggested for multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. As a real attempt to assist eradicate tuberculosis from the planet in the near future, this review article was created following a thorough literature study with the goal of improving knowledge and raising awareness of the disease and adverse drug reaction.

Keywords: Tuberculosis pathogenesis, Tuberculosis diagnosis, Tuberculosis treatment, DOTS

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INTRODUCTION:

The most common infectious disease affecting humans, tuberculosis (TB) is a major cause of illness and mortality globally [1]. tuberculosis (M. tuberculosis) is the primary causative agent of this infectious disease. Although TB mostly affects the lungs, it can also have an impact on the circulatory, lymphatic, and central neurological systems [2-4]. Screening programs and vaccinations like the Bacillus Calmette Guerin (BCG) vaccine are the two major methods of TB prevention [6].

TB is a terrible disease that spreads all over the world due to a lack of adequate treatment. It is the second leading cause of death from an infectious disease worldwide after the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) [9]. A significant number of people with low socioeconomic status and members of marginalized communities have tuberculosis.

Treating tuberculosis is a challenging endeavor that necessitates the long-term administration of several medications. Antibiotic resistance is a growing issue in infections caused by multiple drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB). Additionally, attempts have been made to manage MDR and XDR-TB by combining the right multidrug medication with clinical, radiographic, microbiological, and histopathologic characteristics. Another tactic created by the World Health Organization (WHO) to combat tuberculosis is DOTS (directly observed therapy,

short- course), which consists of particular combinations of anti-TB medications [7]. One growing issue in the treatment of tuberculosis is antibiotic resistance. Regarding the use of first and second line anti-TB medications, the DOTS strategy, and innovative drug delivery devices to address resistance issue. The most recent WHO, CDC, and recommendations for the treatment of tuberculosis are also discussed, as well as the current state of new anti-TB medications and vaccines undergoing clinical testing. In order to prevent the worrying spread of this epidemic because of resistance,. Additionally given are the structural characteristics and therapeutic targets of both new anti-TB molecules in the drug research pipeline and traditional medications. In it drug resistance is form and long term treatment is required and if one time of dose is missed by the patient it required to start whole treatment again . In these studies mainly focus on drug use in treatment isoniazid and Rifampicin and other drugs used are

1. FIRST LINE DRUG: Isoniazid, Rifampicin, Pyrazinamide, Ethambutol, Streptomycin,
2. SECOND LINE DRUG
 - a. Fluoroquinolones Ofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Moxifloxacin, Ciprofloxacin,
 - b. Other oral drugs Ethionamide, Prothionamide, Cycloserine, Terizidone, Para amino salicylic acid (PAS), Rifabutin, Thiacetazone, c. Inject drugs Kanamycin, Amikacin ,Capreomycin able drugs Kanamycin, Amikacin, Caprin.

Types OF TUBERCULOSIS

1. According to state of mycobacterium tuberculosis
 - a. Latent tuberculosis
 - b. Active tuberculosis
2. According to effect on body
 - a. Tubercular lymphadenitis
 - b. Pleural tuberculosis
 - c. Abdominal tuberculosis
 - d. Central nervous system tuberculosis
 - e. Bone and joint tuberculosis
 - f. Genito urinary tuberculosis
 - g. Miliary tuberculosis

PATHOGENESIS:

The primary cause of tuberculosis is a tiny, aerobic, non-motile bacillus called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [15–17]. The typical M. TB complex is made up of tuberculosis and seven closely related mycobacterial species: *M. bovis*, *M. africanum*, *M. microti*, *M. caprae*, *M. pinnipedii*, *M. canetti*, and *M. mungi* [15]. Inhaling even fewer than 10 germs can result in an infection, because the infectious dosage of tuberculosis is extremely low [16, 17].

Tuberculosis is thought to be a granulomatous inflammatory illness that starts when mycobacteria enter the lungs' pulmonary alveoli. The cells that aggregate and create granulomas include macrophages, T lymphocytes, B lymphocytes, and fibroblasts. The infected macrophages encircle the lymphocytes. When bacteria inside the granuloma go dormant, they develop an infection, which ultimately leads to abnormal cell death, or necrosis [2, 17]. Numerous risk factors are important in increasing a person's vulnerability to tuberculosis infections. These include alcoholism, silicosis, cigarette smoke, HIV, diabetes mellitus, malnourishment, and more [18]

SYMPTOMS:

- Chest pain
- Fatigue
- Weight loss
- Night sweats
- Fever

RISK FACTORS

- Diabetes mellitus

- Smoking
- Alcohol use
- Illicit drug use

DIAGNOSIS:

- Radiology technique
- chest X-rays
- microscopic examination
- microbiological culture like multiple sputum cultures.
- skin test
- Interferon gamma release assays (IGRAs) of the blood samples

Epidemiology:

Nearly one-third of the world's population is infected with *M. tuberculosis* bacilli, which carries a 10% lifetime chance of contracting TB illness. 19. 10.4 million TB infections were recorded worldwide in 2017, accounting for to 133 occurrences per one million persons, with 90% of cases occurring in adults (less than 15 years old), 64% in men, and 9% among HIV-positive individuals (72% in Africa) [Fig. 1]. Rifampicin-resistant TB (RR-TB) was estimated to have occurred in 558 000 new cases (range: 483 000–639 000), with nearly half of these cases occurring in three nations: China (13%) India (24%), and the Russian Federation (10%). 6. The majority of the 0.8 million new EPTB cases that were reported globally in 2013—0.35 million—came from India. 20 Data from the Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP) in India indicates that EPTB is 15–20% common in non-HIV patients and 50% common in HIV-positive persons. The lymph nodes where EPTB was distributed. %, belly 10%, pleural cavity 30%, bones and joints 8%, central nervous system 2%, and other areas 3%. 21 There was a 42% decrease in the TB death rate between 2000 and 2017. The incidence of tuberculosis has decreased by 2% annually on average, while the case fatality rate decreased from 23% in 2000 to 16% in 2017. 6. According to the Stop TB Partnership Program, India has succeeded in lowering the prevalence rate by 50% in 30 high-burden nations. Since the early days of ART's debut, drug-resistant TB has been documented; nevertheless, multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) and more recently, widely drug resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) is a danger to the global TB control initiative.

ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS:

Hepatotoxicity:

Acute viral hepatitis and anti-tubercular medication-associated hepatitis share a similar clinical appearance. Hepatotoxicity caused by antitubercular drugs may appear as temporary acute liver failure or an increase in transaminases without any symptoms. In many nations, the prevalence of hepatotoxicity varies between 2% and 39%.⁴⁰ When compared to the Western population, a higher prevalence of hepatotoxicity has been noted in the Indian subpopulation.^{41, 42} It was shown that 11.5% of Indians had drug-induced hepatotoxicity. According to a West analysis, the risk was 4e28%.^{43, 44} Although some people are more susceptible than others, the incidence of drug-induced hepatotoxicity is unpredictable. Factors including advanced age, acute or chronic liver disease, alcoholism, HIV, indiscriminate drug use, malnutrition, hypoproteinemia, hypoalbuminemia, anemia, a history of jaundice, and more advanced tuberculosis have all been linked to the higher incidence in developing nations.^{45–47}

Peripheral Neuropathy:

After receiving H.56, 20% of patients develop peripheral neuropathy. This matched the results of a research conducted in Pakistan that found peripheral neuropathy was defined by The most frequent adverse drug reaction (ADR) seen with H was a burning and tingling sensation in the hands and feet. Although it is much less common than H, E is the other anti-TB medication that is known to induce peripheral neuropathy. According to a research by Koju et al., only 18.57% of patients had peripheral neuropathy.⁵⁷ Peripheral neuropathy is regarded as uncommon in the literature currently in

publication when using the suggested dosages of H in the DOTS approach. Shinde et al.'s research of 893 patients who had begun taking FLDs found that 5.04% of individuals

Optic neuritis:

The most significant possible adverse drug reaction from E is retro-bulbar neuritis. Most of the time, it is reversible and depends on the dosage and length of treatment, although it can occasionally become irreversible, leading to long-term visual impairment, particularly in elderly individuals.⁶⁶ When E is used for more than two months, the incidence of retrobulbar neuritis has been found to be 18% in persons taking more than 35 mg/kg/day, 5–6% with 25 mg/kg/day, and less than 1% with 15 mg/kg/day.^{67,68} Rarely, H and SLDs like Lzd and capreomycin (Cm) are associated with optic neuritis.^{69,70} Optic neuritis caused by LZD is typically irreversible.

Nephrotoxicity:

Because they build up in the renal tubules, aminoglycosides have toxic effects on the kidneys. These side effects are more prevalent in older people and persons with a medical history of renal illness. Additional risk factors for renal damage include prolonged use of aminoglycosides, hepatotoxicity, dehydration, hypotension, and concurrent use of nephrotoxic medications. When utilizing S.^{92,93}, the risk of nephrotoxicity is lower and ranges around 2%. Treatment for DRTB instances is difficult because injectable medications including Km, Am, and Cm are more nephrotoxic than S, with a reported prevalence of 1.2 6.7%. Renal toxicity has been documented for E, Z, and Cs (59,94). Patients with DR-TB who have renal insufficiency can safely use newer medications such as Bdq and Dlm.

Ototoxicity:

While Km and Cm primarily affect the cochlear apparatus, streptomycin (S) primarily affects the vestibular system. According to audiometry statistics, the prevalence of S linked to Ototoxicity could reach 25%. 71 Of a group of 975 children receiving S sulfate treatment for pulmonary tuberculosis, 36% had audiologically identified lesions, according to Prazic and Salaj et al. 72 Infants of tuberculosis moms who received S during pregnancy have also been documented to have hearing damage. 73 There have also been reports of drug-induced toxicity occurring in families. 74 In a large Indian research, 16.1% of patients treated with S who had short-course chemotherapy regimens for pulmonary tuberculosis experienced vertigo, with 5% of those cases being severe. 75 Ten percent of these patients required stopping the medication. **Cardiotoxicity:**

It has been documented that FQs, specifically moxifloxacin (Mfx), macrolides such clarithromycin (Clr), Cfx, Bdq, and Dlm, cause QTc prolongation on electrocardiograms (ECGs). 100,101 Danger Elderly people, women, underlying heart conditions, both congenital and acquired, electrolyte imbalance, and concurrent use of auxiliary drugs are all risk factors for QTc prolongation. According to a systematic study, Bdq is a rather well-tolerated medication because only 3.4% and 0.6% of patients stopped using it because of adverse drug reactions or QTc prolongation, respectively. One hundred

Complications in treatment of TB

- Multiple drug resistance
- Adverse drug reaction
- Non adherence
- Long term treatment required

ISONIAZID:

Isoniazid is a highly effective and most widely used antitubercular agent It is orally effective, cheapest and has tuberculocidal activity, It is active against both intracellular and extracellular bacilli It is also used for chemoprophylaxis of tuberculosis

Mechanism of action:

Action Mechanism Since 1952, isoniazid has been a key component of TB treatment plans. The catalase-peroxidase KatG activates the prodrug INH, forming a range of radicals and adducts that prevent the mycobacterium from producing the mycolic acids that comprise its cell wall. INH has the capacity to be a strong bactericidal agent because of its activity.

Additionally, the medicine seems to work in concert with other TB-treating drugs and other species that KatG produces. [7] However, resistance to INH therapy may result from

mutations in the katG, inhA, kasA, and ahpC genes. With INH monotherapy, M TB resistance develops more quickly. [8] [9]

ADVERSE DRUG REACTION:

INH use has been linked to a number of negative consequences, the majority of which are mild and temporary. In addition to the usual gastrointestinal side effects, some patients additionally develop redness and itching. Even though it occurs less frequently than 0.2% of the time, peripheral neuropathy is another typical side effect of INH therapy. Patients with diabetes, HIV, dietary deficiencies, renal failure, alcoholism, and pregnant or lactating women may be at higher risk. INH metabolites tend to interfere with the metabolism of vitamin B6 (pyridoxine), which lowers the quantities of physiologically active B6. This appears to be the mechanism underlying INH-induced peripheral neuropathy. Therefore, pyridoxine supplementation during treatment is utilized to treat and prevent peripheral neuropathy brought on by INH. [1] [17]

Additionally, INH is a CYP450 inhibitor (2C19: moderate, 3A4: weak), which may raise the serum levels of medications used concurrently, including primidone, phenytoin, carbamazepine, and diazepam. These drug-drug interactions might be more likely to occur with slow acetylation. [18] Up to 1% of people taking INH have been observed to develop drug-induced lupus erythematosus (DILE). Thirty percent of the patients in these circumstances have pericarditis, and half have fever and pleuritis. Slow acetylation may raise the chance of developing INH-induced lupus, according to some specialists. [19] The majority of drug-induced lupus cases have positive anti-histone antibodies. [20] Severe encephalopathy is more likely to occur in patients receiving prolonged hemodialysis. [21]

Drug-Drug Relationship As a CYP450 inhibitor, INH may cause increased serum levels of medications like primidone and diazepam. These drug-drug interactions may be more likely to occur in slow acetylators. [18] INH raises phenytoin's plasma levels. Therefore, it is recommended to adjust the dosage of phenytoin in order to prevent toxicity. [22] Concurrent dosing of INH has been linked to increased acetaminophen toxicity. Glutathione is reduced as a result of INH's increased metabolism of acetaminophen. INH is also a strong CYP2E1 inducer, which results in the formation of harmful metabolites and hepatotoxicity.

[23] Because INH prevents carbamazepine from being metabolized, its levels and toxicity rise. As a result, it is advised to modify the carbamazepine dosage. [16]

Theophylline plasma levels may rise when INH is administered with theophylline. Therapeutic drug monitoring is advised because theophylline has a narrow therapeutic index. [24] When using INH concurrently, the intravenous bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine should not be administered. [25]

CONTRAINDICATION:

When theophylline is given with INH, theophylline plasma levels may increase. Theophylline has a limited therapeutic index, hence therapeutic drug monitoring is recommended. [24]

The intravenous bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine should not be given when taking INH. [25]

ENHANCING HEALTHCARE TEAM OUTCOME:

Clinicians treating TB patients with INH must be aware of the patient's baseline liver function and the hepatotoxic risks associated with INH. Although estimates of fatal hepatitis associated with INH treatment are only 0.023%, these cases correlate with continued administration despite symptoms of hepatitis during treatment.[1] TB has widespread effects and greatly burdens individual patients and communities. Appropriate treatment is crucial for limiting the spread of TB and preventing drug resistance. Therefore, a clinician treating TB prescribes the appropriate treatment regimen and ensures adequate treatment adherence and completion.[1] A growing concern is INH-resistant strains of TB, and it appears that these may serve as precursors to multidrug-resistant strains. Thus, clinicians should monitor patient progress to promptly detect patients not responding to INH treatment and who may harbor a resistant strain. INH-resistant strains require an altered regimen and increased efforts to prevent disease transmission.[34][35]

Public health departments typically provide TB treatment. They frequently collaborate as part of an interprofessional healthcare team with other entities such as private providers, community health centers, shelters, and others to ensure the completion of treatment. The interprofessional team should use a patient-centered approach to tailor a treatment plan specific to each patient's needs to provide the best opportunity for treatment completion. This approach often involves social workers, case managers, and medical

professionals; optimal communication and coordination of services are essential. One way for the team to maximize adherence is through direct observation of therapy (DOT), in which healthcare professionals provide the medications directly to the patient and watch as they swallow them. This approach has become the preferred method of drug administration for TB

Nurses and pharmacists are also valuable members of this interprofessional approach by verifying doses, providing patient counsel, monitoring therapeutic progress, ensuring medication compliance, and monitoring adverse events. Nurses can use the DOT method to ensure medication compliance. Consultation from obstetricians is necessary for TB in pregnancy. Pediatricians play an essential role in the overall management of TB in children. Infectious disease consultation is crucial for multidrug-resistant TB and nontuberculous mycobacterial pulmonary disease. Interprofessional coordination and collaboration among physicians, advanced practice practitioners, specialists, pharmacists, nurses, and public health professionals can enhance patient outcomes when using INH therapy in treating TB infection.

RIFAMPICIN:

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Rifampicin inhibits DNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RNAP) to produce bactericidal antimicrobial actions. This suppression happens either by decreasing the RNAP's affinity for short RNA transcripts or by sterically blocking the elongating RNA's route at its 5' end. Rifampicin efficiently stops ongoing RNA synthesis by specifically targeting microbial RNAP.

[16] [17] The range of possible negative effects in humans is reduced since rifampicin has no effect on the mammalian RNAP enzyme. Furthermore, rifampicin has bactericidal effects against *M. tuberculosis*, both extracellularly and intracellularly. [18] Elevated bile acid levels are the primary cause of the pruritus seen in cholestatic disorders such as primary biliary cirrhosis. Rifampicin antipruritic effects, which are especially beneficial in cholestatic diseases, are accomplished by upregulating microsomal enzymes, specifically cytochrome P3A (CYP3A). Bile acids are hydroxylated as a result of this enzymatic overexpression. Bile acids' hydroxylation reduces the ileum's ability to reabsorb them, which further relieves pruritic symptoms. [19]

ADVERSE DRUG REACTION:

Rifampicin can have side effects that are either dose-dependent or dose-independent, even though patients typically tolerate the medication well. Due to its excretion in bodily fluids, rifampicin can cause dose-dependent side effects, such as orange staining of tears, which can discolour contact lenses, sweat, saliva, urine, and faeces. Additionally linked are gastrointestinal problems like diarrhoea, anorexia, and nausea. [30] Tests for *C. difficile* infection should be performed to rule out the likelihood of rifampicin-induced pseudomembranous colitis in patients, even though diarrhoea is a rare side effect of the medication. In these cases, it has been noted that stopping rifampicin and adding metronidazole significantly reduces symptoms.

The most common side effect of using rifampicin to treat pruritus linked to primary biliary cirrhosis is constipation. [32] Patients receiving rifampicin for pruritus have also been known to develop asymptomatic hepatitis. [33] There is a chance of hepatotoxicity, especially in people who already have liver disease. Despite being hepatocellular, the pattern of enzyme increase can appear mixed or cholestatic. [34] Hypersensitive reactions such as urticaria, flu-like symptoms, thrombocytopenia, hemolysis, and renal failure are examples of dose-independent side effects of rifampicin. Intermittent or prolonged use of rifampicin increases the risk of these hypersensitivity events. When rifampicin is stopped, many of the side effects stated above usually go away. [35] [30] Pneumonitis caused by rifampicin, which is comparable to COVID-19 pneumonia, has been documented. [36] Rifampicin is a strong inducer of the cytochrome P450 enzyme. To prevent any dampening effects of simultaneously delivered medicines in combination with rifampicin, a comprehensive examination of the patient's pharmaceutical regimen should be performed. [37] Drug transporter proteins including hepatic P-glycoprotein and a variety of drug-metabolizing enzymes, including cytochrome P450 (CYP) 3A4, are also strongly stimulated by the drug. Because of this property, rifampicin may be less effective when used with other medications, which could limit its use. HIV protease inhibitors, antimycotics like itraconazole and ketoconazole, cyclosporine, which can cause graft rejections, calcium channel blockers like verapamil, nifedipine, and diltiazem, sulfonyleureas, oral contraceptives, and warfarin are among the medications that are frequently involved. It typically takes a week or so after starting rifampicin for the stimulation of drug-metabolizing enzymes to produce interactions that

are clinically meaningful. Furthermore, this effect lasts for about two weeks after stopping rifampicin. [38] The following medications may have major side effects if used with rifampicin: By inducing CYP3A4, rifampicin significantly lowers the amounts of oxycodone, morphine, and methadone, which may result in opioid withdrawal. As a result, dosage modifications are required. [39] [40] Simvastatin's plasma levels is decreased by concurrent use of rifampicin because it induces CYP3A4. [41] By inducing CYP3A4, rifampicin dramatically raises quinine clearance. [42] By inducing CYP2C19, rifampicin raises the concentration of clopidogrel's active metabolite, which may increase the risk of bleeding. Rifampicin, on the other hand, decreases the efficiency of ticagrelor by lowering its concentrations through the activation of the CYP3A4 enzyme. Therefore, using these medications at the same time should be avoided. [43] [44] The stimulation of CYP2C8 by rifampicin results in a decrease in the concentration of rosiglitazone. As a result, using both drugs at the same time requires cautious thought. [45] By inducing CYP2C9, rifampicin lowers the concentrations of glipizide and glyburide and may exacerbate glycemia control. Therefore, care should be used when using it. [46] The concentration and exposure (AUC) of telithromycin are considerably reduced when rifampicin is administered concurrently with telithromycin. Therefore, it is best to refrain from using them at the same time. [47] As a P-glycoprotein inducer, rifampicin can lower the blood levels of direct oral anticoagulants (DOAC), such as apixaban, rivaroxaban, and dabigatran. Therefore, care should be used when using them together. [48] [49] [50] According to the European Heart Rhythm recommendations, using DOACs in addition to rifampicin requires caution and close observation. [51] Metoprolol and propranolol's plasma levels and effectiveness are decreased by rifampicin. [52] [53] Because rifampicin is a UGT1A1 inducer, it may result in lower levels of raltegravir and cabotegravir. Therefore, it is best to avoid taking these medications at the same time. [54] [55] Because of the higher risk of hepatotoxicity, rifampicin should not be administered concurrently with hepatotoxic medications like halothane. [56] It is not advised to take rifampicin at the same time as some antiviral medications used to treat hepatitis C, such as daclatasvir, simeprevir, sofosbuvir, and telaprevir. According to available evidence, this combination is contraindicated since it dramatically lowers plasma concentrations. [57]

CONTRAINDICATION:

One significant contraindication to medication use is a history of allergy to rifampicin or other rifamycin, including rifabutin, rifaximin, and rifapentine. Rifampicin should not be used in the treatment regimen for drug-resistant TB, especially rifampicin-resistant TB or polydrug-resistant TB. To guarantee proper therapy, antibiotic susceptibility testing for tuberculosis should be carried out. [58] Patients on fosamprenavir, atazanavir, darunavir, tipranavir, and saquinavir should not use rifampicin. This is because rifampin can decrease these medications' concentrations, which lessens their antiviral efficacy and raises the possibility of the emergence of viral resistance. [59] Because of the possibility of severe hepatotoxicity, rifampicin should not be used with ritonavir-boosted saquinavir regimens. [60] It is not advised to use rifampicin and praziquantel at the same time since this may cause praziquantel levels to drop and result in treatment failure.

ENHANCE HEALTH CARE OUTCOME:

Bacterial resistance to rifampicin, a commonly used antimicrobial drug, is becoming increasingly common. Rifampicin should therefore be used in combination with other antimicrobial medicines, especially in cases of specific illnesses like tuberculosis or when the bacterial organism's sensitivity to rifampicin has been determined. To prevent significant drug interactions, the interprofessional healthcare team should obtain a thorough drug history. Patients should be made aware of the moderate and severe side effects of rifampicin and advised to get help right away if they encounter any of them.

Since rifampicin is prescribed for diseases like leprosy and tuberculosis that require prolonged care, the interprofessional healthcare team should make sure that patients are informed about the importance of following the recommended dosage and frequency of administration. For the correct use of rifampicin to reduce the possibility of antibiotic resistance, clinicians who treat infectious disorders should be contacted.

According to recent studies, involving trained pharmacists who treat infectious diseases can improve antimicrobial stewardship program adherence. [72] By rapidly alerting prescribing clinicians to any adverse reactions, interactions, or signs of therapeutic failure, the nursing staff plays a crucial role in rifampicin therapy. For rifampicin

treatment to be successful, all interprofessional team members must communicate openly. When it comes to evaluating patient compliance, social workers can help. To guarantee that drug distribution procedures are followed in accordance with suggested criteria, good communication between doctors, advanced practice practitioners, specialists, pharmacists, and nursing personnel is essential in an inpatient setting. In order to maximize results and minimize issues, the interprofessional healthcare team makes sure that patient-centered care is provided.

How to overcome the adverse effect of Isoniazid and Rifampin :

Dietary guidelines play a crucial role in the management of tuberculosis (TB). Consuming the right foods can help boost the immune system, aid recovery and prevent further complications. Here are some dietary guidelines to consider:

1. Consume foods high in protein.

Protein is essential for the body's tissue growth, repair, and maintenance; TB sufferers need more protein to help them recover. Good sources of protein include foods high in protein, such as eggs, lean meat, chicken, fish, beans, lentils, and nuts. Eating foods high in protein can boost immunity, encourage healing, and stop muscle loss.

2. Eat Foods High in Calories

TB patients often require extra calories to help aid recovery. Eating foods high in calories can provide you the energy you need. Some high-calorie foods that can be included in the Tuberculosis diet are avocados, cheese, nuts, peanut butter, whole milk, yoghurt, dried fruits, dark chocolate and granola bars. It's important to consume these foods in moderation and not rely on them exclusively for calorie intake.

3. Eat Micronutrients

Essential nutrients known as micronutrients are needed in trace levels for general health and wellbeing. Among these are vitamins and minerals, which are essential for immune system maintenance, recuperation, and averting more issues. Eating foods high in micronutrients, such as citrus fruits, berries, dark green leafy vegetables, nuts, and seeds, can help guarantee that the body is getting the nutrition it needs to operate correctly.

4. Eat Superfoods

Superfoods with anti-inflammatory and immune-boosting qualities, such as green tea, ginger, garlic, and turmeric, can help control tuberculosis. Curcumin, an ingredient in turmeric, has been shown to have antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties. Green tea is high in antioxidants, and garlic and ginger offer immune-boosting qualities that can aid in the battle against infections.

5. Eat Foods High in Energy

Patients with tuberculosis may lose weight, feel nauseous, and lose their appetite, which can cause weakness and exhaustion. High-energy foods that are easy to digest, such as soups, stews, and smoothies, can supply the nutrients that are needed. These foods can be high in healthy fats, protein, and carbs, giving you the energy you need to help heal and avoid more problems.

6. Emphasis on Healthful Carbs

A balanced diet must include good carbohydrates, particularly for TB patients. Complex carbohydrates, like those found in whole-grain bread, pasta, and brown rice, are good for you since they are high in fiber and minerals. These foods give the body long-lasting energy and aid in blood sugar stabilization, avoiding spikes and crashes that can cause exhaustion and weakness

7. Invest in Good Fats

Investing in good fats is important for TB patients as they need healthy sources of energy to aid in recovery. Good fats, such as those found in avocados, nuts, seeds and olive oil, are rich in essential fatty acids that can help improve heart health, brain function and immune system function. These fats can also help regulate inflammation in the body, which can help TB patients reduce the risk of developing complications.

8. Ensure Taking Ample

Vegetables and Minerals Vegetables are a great source of vitamins and minerals that can help boost the immune system and aid recovery in TB patients. Dark green leafy vegetables, such as spinach and kale, are rich in vitamins A, C and vitamins K, as well as iron and calcium. Other vegetables like carrots, sweet potatoes and bell peppers are high in antioxidants and fibre, which can help prevent cell damage and improve digestive health.

9. Foods Rich in B-Complex

Vitamins B-complex vitamins are important for maintaining good health, especially in the context of tuberculosis management. Foods rich in B-complex vitamins include leafy green vegetables, whole grains, nuts and seeds, legumes, dairy products, meat, fish and poultry. Consuming a balanced diet with these foods can help support the immune system and promote overall health during TB treatment.

10. Foods Rich in Zinc

Zinc is an essential mineral that plays a crucial role in maintaining a healthy immune system, wound healing and growth and development. Some foods that are rich in zinc include oysters, beef, pork, chicken, nuts, beans, whole grains and dairy products. Adequate intake of zinc is particularly important for individuals with TB, as zinc

deficiency can impair immune function and increase susceptibility to infection.

CONCLUSIONS:

Several attempts have been made to manage MDR and XDR-TB by combining the right multidrug medication with clinical, radiographic, microbiological, and histopathologic characteristics. Types of tuberculosis are enlisted according to state of mycobacterium tuberculosis and according to effect on body seven closely related mycobacterial species: *M. bovis*, *M. africanum*, *M. microti*, *M. caprae*, *M. pinnipedii*, *M. canetti*, and *M. mungi*. Epidemiology states that Nearly one-third of the world's population is infected with *M. tuberculosis bacilli*, which carries a 10% lifetime chance of contracting TB illness. Treatment with antitubercular medication shows adverse drug reactions hepatotoxicity, peripheral neuropathy, optic neuritis, nephrotoxicity, cardiotoxicity. Most commonly used drug for treatment is Isoniazid works to treat tb by inhibiting mycolic acid production. ADR associated with INZ is that it inhibits CYP450 enzyme so it increase half life period of drugs. So it increase more chances of causing ADR of other drugs. To avoid this adverse effect therapy management is done by improving treatment regimen. Moa of rifampicin is it inhibits DNA-dependent RNA polymerase enzyme. Ad-Hepatitis, Pneumonitis treatment regimen is managed. To guarantee that drug distribution procedures are followed in accordance with suggested criteria, good communication between doctors, advanced practice practitioners, specialists, pharmacists, and nursing personnel is essential in an inpatient setting. In order to maximize results and minimize issues, the interprofessional healthcare team makes sure that patient-centered care is provided. Dietary guidelines to manage TB involves high protein and calorie diet, having micronutrients rich in vitamin and minerals, eating super foods with anti-inflammatory and immune boosting qualities, diet rich in zinc, b complex and good fats

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